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RWD and RWE - the Promise and Problems

Happy spring!

As we step into the vibrant season, we are thrilled to share this newsletter about the latest development and initiatives from our IDSWG oncology working group. It has been an exciting journey so far, filled with innovation, collaboration, and impactful research aimed at advancing our understanding and treatment of cancer.

The current edition of the newsletter features real-world data (RWD) and real-world evidence (RWE) in addition to sections on FDA approvals, recent ODAC meetings, Biostat Bytes and WG updates. RWD is observational data and includes electronic health records (EHRs), medical claims data, data from product or disease registries, and data gathered from other sources (such as digital health technologies) that can inform on health status [1]. The popularity of RWD use for RWE has grown due to advancements in data sharing and cloud computing. These advancements have enabled the industry to leverage large, complex datasets more effectively and efficiently, leading to the emergence of new data strategies and methodologies. Dr. Sajan Khosla from AstraZeneca covers details of RWE in the pharmaceutical industry in the KOL message.

Since 2017, FDA stepped up the development of RWD/RWE guidance documents and released 10 guidance documents covering data sources, study design, and regulatory submissions. These guidance documents advise that the generation and utilization of RWD and RWE meet certain standards of reliability, validity, and relevance for informing regulatory decisions. An introduction to RWD data sources and a high-level non-exhaustive summary of recent regulatory filings using RWD are included in this newsletter. One ODAC meeting on October 4 is particularly interesting about eflornithine in high-risk neuroblastoma based on a study that used external control and obtained ODAC votes 14:6 in favor of eflornithine improving event-free survival and the drug was subsequently approved in December 2023. The Biostat Bytes panel explains several statistical terms used in RWD/RWE including immortal time bias, hybrid trial, and externally controlled trial.

There are multifaceted purposes of RWD to improve the statistical efficiency in trial design [2-3], trial recruitment [4], health technology assessment (HTA) and reimbursement submissions [5-6] and in generalizing research findings in subgroup representation [7]. Furthermore RWD from multiple healthcare databases can be linked together for monitoring of drug safety as in FDA's sentinel initiative [8] and the assessment of the real-world health outcomes in European health data and evidence network (EHDEN) project [9].

Given the promise of Real-World Data (RWD) and Real-World Evidence (RWE) in drug development, numerous methodological challenges await statistical solutions. There are two substreams within IDSWG focusing on addressing issues and implementation of RWD in oncology research. We hope to share some of the work and findings from these groups in the near future.

Stay well, stay safe wherever you are!

Co-chairs

Dr. Philip He

Dr. Laura Fernandes

See page 4 for reference

*IDSWG: Innovative Designs Scientific Working Group <https://oncotrialdesign.github.io>

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KOL Message: Real World Evidence for Pharmaceutical Research and Development

By Sajan Khosla †

Real World Evidence (RWE) is a broad term that has been adopted within the pharmaceutical industry due to its ability to bring together two complex sub terms; the Real World Data (RWD) and the Evidence subsequently synthesised from those data. Therefore to truly define RWE one must define the RWD. RWD in its most traditional form is data collected in routine clinical practice that contains information pertinent to a patients' health status [1]. The evidence generated is a result of statistical, epidemiological and scientifically robust methodologies that can make use of these data.

With this definition and this understanding of RWE it becomes clearer to explain the variety in the types of skills required within industry to deliver innovative RWE and also why RWE is not just one thing, as the permutations of sources of data together with the types of analysis lead us into hundreds if not thousands of types of RWE designs.

The popularity of RWE within the pharmaceutical industry stems from the value the capability has brought into the industry, starting from traditional pharmacovigilance with safety focused epidemiology. The expansion into Medical Affairs with post marketing commitments with the use of RWE and the use of RWE to fill evidence gaps that emerge from randomised clinical trials. The primary inflection point being in the early 2010's where the notion of scalable data sharing or acquisition became a reality. Industry teams developed statistical infrastructure to house large complicated medical claims datasets and developed a traditional "Stats and Programming" capability around those data. The second inflection point was cloud computing, when it was realised these large complex data that often took two to three days worth of processing to run a single script, could be done in milliseconds, a dynamic shift was observed with how the industry could use these data. With that data strategies and ultimately types of methodologies emerged and evolved as the industry had the ability to balance out that benefit vs. resource risk.

The view so far has been introspective from an industry view but outside industry academic partners, data owners and health systems were also experiencing their own market forces that evolved their depth and expertise. Especially in academia where public health units started to specialise in causal modelling methods [2], capabilities like target trial emulation [3] and the multi purpose use of Propensity Score Weighting/Matching [4] became clear.

"With that maturity in the use of RWE over the past decade, nuances of how to position RWE in the pre-regulatory domain is more clearly defined..."

The value cycle of RWE has also shifted with the change in types of data that feed into our evidence packages and the methodologies that are available for the industry to deploy. With that maturity in the use of RWE over the past decade, nuances of how to position RWE in the pre-regulatory domain is more clearly defined to its counterpart in the post-regulatory marketing space, where RWE has traditionally been organised.

A personal hope for RWE is that this evolution in the types of data follows a path by which health systems become more sophisticated in the variety of RWD that is available, to some extent this is happening with use of data linkage and tokenisation [5]. This evolution of the data brings a rise in the methodologies we deploy to robustly assess and evaluate RWE, such as Quantitative Bias Analysis (QBA) [6]. This together with the evolving structure global regulators are developing to allow for RWE packages to be evaluated as part of the approval process gives me confidence that the evolution of the term RWE is not over.

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† About the author: Sajan Khosla, is the Head of Late Data Science and Real World Evidence within Oncology R&D at AstraZeneca. In this role he is responsible for the development of a unique and innovative Data Science and RWE unit that focuses the spectrum of RWE capabilities upon the pressing challenges of an R&D; supporting the investment in Real World Data, Machine Learning & AI, technologies and platforms that accelerate the analysis of these data and the build out of Real World Evidence capability and enabling the innovative use of these data. Ultimately to support decision making within the pipeline and advance innovative medicines with evidence for the regulators.

Dahshu IDSWG Oncology Working Group Highlights

- Launch of a new taskforce: *Optimizing Clinical Trial Conduct*
- Master protocol ISBS presentation by Cindy Lu
- Submitted public comments to FDA Draft Guidance Documents: *Master Protocols for Drug and Biological Product Development*. <https://www.regulations.gov/comment/FDA-2023-D-5259-0020>
- JSM Session: *Examples and Perspectives Using Machine Learning and Artificial Intelligence in Drug Development*
- Multiple manuscripts submitted in adaptive design

Upcoming Conferences

- [The 9th Workshop on Biostatistics and Bioinformatics](#), May 3-5, 2024, Atlanta, Georgia State University, GA
- [The 7th Stat4Onc Annual Symposium](#), May 8-11, 2024, University of Connecticut, Storrs, CT
- [2024 Symposium on Data Science & Statistics](#), June 4-7, 2024, Richmond, Virginia
- [2024 WVAR/IMS/Graybill Annual Meeting](#), June 9-12, 2024, Fort Collins, Colorado
- [ICSA Applied Statistics Symposium](#), June 16-19, 2024, Nashville, Tennessee
- [PSJ](#), June 17-19, 2024, Amsterdam
- [DIA Annual Meeting](#), June 16-20, 2024, San Diego, CA
- [JSM](#), August 3-8, 2024, Portland, Oregon
- [ASA BIOP Regulatory-Industry Statistics Workshop](#), Sept. 25-27, 2024, Rockville, Maryland

Introduction to Real-World Data (RWD) Sources

By Yoko Tanaka†

RWD are data related to patient health status and/or the delivery of health care routinely collected from a variety of sources.

Typical examples of RWD include data derived from electronic health records (EHR), medical claims data, and data from product or disease registries[1].

EHR database contains individual patient record and can provide comprehensive and diverse information from multiple sources within the healthcare system, including medical history, diagnoses, treatment plans, pathology reports, laboratory results, medication records, and provider notes. They usually contain rich information that may not be available from other types of RWD e.g. detailed information on cancer diagnoses, tumor characteristics, treatment plans, and outcomes. Information held within EHRs may be maintained in unstructured text documents and require curation and translation to structured data. However, they do not include comprehensive information on health care provided outside the facility covered by the system such as imaging data.

Claims contain individual patient data recorded for reimbursement purposes including information on diagnoses and services during patient visits from claims for insurance providers. There are open and closed claims type, and open claims data is derived from broad-based healthcare sources and can highlight a patient's activities over a longer timeframe, regardless of a patient's insurance provider. Closed payer claims data is derived from health insurance providers (payers), adjudicated patient's healthcare information during a specific enrollment period. They can provide longitudinal features which enable a clear description of a population over time. They usually contain patient health data across different health care settings, including inpatient visits, outpatient visits, pharmacy etc. They allow analyzing patterns of healthcare utilization, healthcare resource allocation, and associated costs. However, health care services that are not reimbursable by the health plan or program may not be captured.

Registries are designed to collect uniform and systematic clinical data for a specific population of patients with particular disease, including drug exposure, disease, or outcome. Registries also enroll a specific population to collect prespecified patient-level health-related data. They collect unique information not available from other sources, such as detailed and targeted exposure data and patient-reported outcomes using the Case Report Forms (CRFs) which ensure consistent and uniform data collection across different sites or regions. However, some registries may not capture data on care provided outside the system in which the registry is based, similar to the limitations of EHR data.

†Reference

- [1] <https://www.fda.gov/science-research/science-and-research-special-topics/real-world-evidence>
 [2] https://friendsofcancerresearch.org/wp-content/uploads/2023-ASCO-Poster-6595_McKelvey.pdf

EHR and claims data can be available from the companies who provide technology and services to harmonize and normalize the data from the various sources or EHR interfaces. For example, seven RWD EHR-focused partners (ConcertAI, COTA, Flatiron Health, Guardian Research Network/IQVIA, Ontada, Syapse, and Tempus) were included in the recent FOCR pilot project presented at American Society of Clinical Oncology (ASCO) Annual Meeting in 2023[2]; and Medical Data Vision[3] in Japan. There are different data products from these companies, some are basic data from the structured sources, some include deeply curated data such as progression and response, and some include additional molecular, biomarker data. Deciding which data product to obtain depends on the research question, availability of the needed data, and budget. Registry data can be available from the registry directly following the registry specific process for request and review[4]. Some RWD, e.g. RWD operated by public institutions, are limited to academic use only or have stringent usage conditions.

Besides relevance of the data source to the research question, other considerations in selecting a RWD source are completeness, comprehensiveness, contemporaneousness and the geographic region of collection. The data product is usually specific to a patient population in a country where the patient medical/claims records are available as in US, Japan, and countries in the European Union (EU). Consideration should be given in the decision of data product which geographic region is of most interest for the purpose of the study.

[3] <https://en.mdv.co.jp/>

[4] https://seer.cancer.gov/data/access_seer_data.pdf

Recent Regulatory Submissions Using RWD in Oncology

By Philip He, PhD† and Laura Fernandes, PhD‡

Table 1. Recent Regulatory Submissions Using RWD in Oncology (FDA)

Drug	Therapeutic Area	Year	RWD Source	RWD Use
Blinatumomab ¹	Ph+ R/R B-cell precursor (BCP) ALL	2014	CRF from trials sites	ECA for SA trial
Avelumab ²	Metastatic Merkel cell carcinoma (MCC)	2017	EHR and registry data	ECA for SA trial
Blinatumomab ³	(MRD+) ALL R/R BCP	2018	CRF from trials sites	ECA for SA trial
Pembrolizumab and lenvatinib ⁴	Endometrial carcinoma	2019	Historical controls	Isolation of treatment effect
Selinexor ⁵	Relapsed refractory multiple myeloma (RRMM)	2019	EHR	ECA for SA trial
Erdafitinib ⁶	FGFR2/3+ mUC	2019	EHR data from US community-based cancer clinics	ECA for SA trial
Palbociclib ⁷	Breast cancer males	2019	EHR	ECA for SA trial
Idecabtagene vicleuce ⁸	Multiple Myeloma	2020	Pooled EHR data	ECA for SA trial
Selumetinib ⁹	Neurofibromatosis type 1 with inoperable plexiform neurofibromas (pediatric)	2020	Historical controls	Establish natural history
Omburtamab ⁹	Neuroblastoma	2022	Central German Childhood Cancer Registry	ECA for SA trial
Eflornithine ¹⁰	High-risk neuroblastoma	2023	Historical clinical trial data	ECA for SA trial

Note: This list is not exhaustive. SA = single arm

Table 1 lists the recent regulatory submissions using RWD to FDA in oncology. The ODAC meeting on October 4, 2023 is particularly interesting about eflornithine in high-risk neuroblastoma who have completed multiagent, multimodality therapy, where external control arm was used to demonstrate the significant effectiveness. In this case, the natural history of the disease has been established by prior clinical trials and external control data source is clinical trial data, verified by FDA inspections. The ODAC voting was 14:6 in favor of eflornithine improving event-free survival and FDA approved the indication in December 2023. Wang et al (2023) summarized the EMA oncology approvals using external controls from 2016 to 2021. Majority of RWD use cases are for understanding of historical benchmark or natural history of disease.

†Daiichi Sankyo Inc. ‡COTA, Inc.

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- [7] FDA Review Palbociclib 2019. Accessed March 30, 2024, https://www.accessdata.fda.gov/drugsatfda_docs/nda/2019/207103Orig1s008.pdf.
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- [9] ODAC FDA Briefing Document Omburtamab 2022. Accessed March 30, 2024, <https://www.fda.gov/media/162614/download>
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FDA Oncologic Drugs Advisory Committee (ODAC) 2023 - Q1' 2024

Click the links to access to the FDA's official review materials

Date	Drug	Company	Indication	Vote Result	YouTube Link
2/9/2023	dostarlimab-gxly	GSK	rectal cancer	8:5 in favor of benefit	YouTube
3/9/2023	polatuzumab vedotin-piiq	Genentech	large B-cell lymphoma	11:2 in favor of benefit	YouTube
4/28/2023	olaparib	AstraZeneca	metastatic castration-resistant prostate cancer	11:1 in favor of restricting to patients with BRCA-mutant (BRCAm) tumors only	YouTube
6/16/2023	dosage optimization of new drug and biological products for pediatric patients with cancer		variability in pharmacokinetic and pharmacodynamic parameters by age and size, the need for age-appropriate formulations, potential for toxicities associated with long-term use, and the rarity of pediatric cancers	Vote was not requested	YouTube
10/4/2023	eflornithine	USWM	high-risk neuroblastoma	14:6 in favor of benefit	YouTube
10/5/2023	sotorasib	Amgen	advanced or metastatic non-small cell lung cancer	10:2 that the progression-free survival of sotorasib (vs. docetaxel) cannot be reliably interpreted	YouTube
11/16/2023	pralatrexate and belinostat	Acrotech Biopharma	peripheral T-cell lymphoma	Vote was not requested	YouTube
3/14/2024	imetelstat	Geron Corporation	transfusion-dependent anemia	12:2 in favor of benefit	YouTube
3/15/2024	ciltacabtagene autoleucel	Janssen Biotech	multiple myeloma	11:0 in favor of benefit	YouTube
3/15/2024	idecabtagene vicleucel	BMS	multiple myeloma	8:3 in favor of benefit	YouTube

FDA Oncology Approvals in Q1 2024

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Date	Generic Name	Indication
3/22/2024	soravtansine-gynx	FRα positive, platinum-resistant epithelial ovarian, fallopian tube, or primaryperitoneal cancer, who have received one to three prior systemic treatmentregimens.
3/19/2024	ponatinib	newly diagnosed Philadelphia chromosome-positive acute lymphoblastic leukemia (Ph+ ALL) in combination with chemotherapy
3/7/2024	zanubrutinib	relapsed/refractory follicular lymphoma after two or more lines of systemic therapy with obinutuzumab
3/7/2024	nivolumab	unresectable or metastatic urothelial carcinoma in combination with cisplatin and gemcitabine
3/6/2024	inotuzumab ozogamicin	pediatric patients 1 year and older with relapsed or refractory CD22-positive B-cell precursor acute lymphoblastic leukemia
3/1/2024	amivantamab-vmjw	locally advanced or metastatic non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) with epidermal growth factor receptor (EGFR) exon 20 insertion mutations in combination with arboplatin and pemetrexed
2/16/2024	osimertinib	locally advanced or metastatic non-small cell lung cancer (la/mNSCLC) whose tumors have EGFR exon 19 deletions or exon 21 L858R mutations
2/16/2024	lifileucel	unresectable or metastatic melanoma previously treated with a PD-1 blocking antibody, and if BRAF V600 positive, a BRAF inhibitor with or without a MEK inhibitor.
2/15/2024	tepotinib	metastatic non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) harboring mesenchymal-epithelial transition (MET) exon 14 skipping alterations.
2/13/2024	irinotecan liposome	metastatic pancreatic adenocarcinoma in combination with oxaliplatin, fluorouracil, and leucovorin
1/18/2024	erdafitinib	locally advanced or metastatic urothelial carcinoma (mUC) with susceptible FGFR3 genetic alterations
1/12/2024	pembrolizumab	FIGO 2014 Stage III-IVA cervical cancer with chemoradiotherapy

DahShu IDSWG Oncology Working Group

FDA Guidance on RWD and RWE

Click the links to access to the FDA's official materials.

Use of Electronic Health Records in Clinical Investigations (2018).	RWD
Real-World Data: Assessing Electronic Health Records and Medical Claims Data to Support Regulatory Decision-Making for Drug and Biological Products (2021).	RWD
Data Standards for Drug and Biological Production Submissions Containing Real-World Data (2021).	Submission
Real-World Data: Assessing Registries to Support Regulatory Decision-Making for Drug and Biological Products (2021).	RWD
Considerations for the Use of Real-World Data and Real-World Evidence to Support Regulatory Decision-Making for Drug and Biological Products (2023).	Submission
Submitting Documents Utilizing Real-World Data and Real-World Evidence to FDA for Drugs and Biologics (2022).	Submission
Considerations for the Design and Conduct of Externally Controlled Trials for Drug and Biological Products (2023).	Design
Use of Real-World Evidence to Support Regulatory Decision-Making for Medical Devices (2017).	Design
Real-World Evidence: Considerations Regarding Non-Interventional Studies for Drug and Biological Products (2024).	Design
Rare Diseases: Natural History Studies for Drug Development (2019).	Design

Hybrid Trial & External Control Trial

By Kristine Broglio, Ph.D. †

The randomized clinical trial of a treatment versus a control arm is typically the gold standard for generating confirmatory evidence of safety and efficacy. However, there are many settings where randomizing patients to a control arm therapy may be infeasible or unethical. Examples include rare diseases, pediatrics, or any other settings with high unmet medical need. There are clinical trial designs that supplement or replace the control arm that would be a randomized trial with data from sources outside the clinical trial.

A **hybrid trial** is a randomized clinical trial where the randomization ratio often favors the treatment arm and data from outside the trial are used to augment the control arm [1].

An **externally controlled trial** assigns all patients to the treatment and uses data from outside the trial to replace the control arm entirely [2].

The data from outside the trial, i.e., the external control data may come from other clinical trials, diseases registries, claims data, or other real world data sources.

When evaluating the use of external data in these trial designs, important considerations include the data quality, the treatments received, and similarity in terms of the patient characteristics and the ascertainment of endpoints.

Reference:

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[2] FDA Draft Guidance: Considerations for the Design and Conduct of Externally Controlled Trials for Drug and Biological Products, February 2023

† AstraZeneca.

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Immortal Time Bias – why do OSCAR winners live longer?

By Binbing Yu, Ph.D. †

In observational studies and clinical trials with survival endpoints, there may be a delay or waiting period before a subject begins to receive a treatment. For example, a patient with kidney failure has to be alive until the day of kidney transplantation, thus the life expectancy of the transplanted group patient is artificially prolonged compared to those un-transplanted.

An OSCAR winner needs to establish a successful career to receive the OSCAR award, if you assume receiving OSCAR as a treatment [1].

This delay period is called "**immortal time**" because, by design, subjects in the treated group must survive a period of time in order to receive the treatment. Ignoring this selection process will lead to bias in the treatment effect estimate, which is called "**immortal time bias**" [2].

Various methods, including Cox model with time-varying covariates, landmark analysis, have been used to correct for the bias [3].

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Biostat Bytes

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